

UP-CYCLING AS METHOD OF SUSTAINABLE TRANSFORMATION: REVISITING SESC POMPEIA

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ABSTRACT

The most sustainable building is the one that already exists. Modernity and sustainability are closely intertwined in the challenge of creating better places to live and work. There is an opportunity (and duty) to preserve the existing fabric and reuse buildings which have lost their original function or no longer meet today's increasingly demanding standards. It is estimated that 80 per cent of buildings in existence today globally will still be there in twenty years' time, therefore it is the physical improvements and adaptive reuse ('up-cycling') of our existing buildings and infrastructure that will contribute in delivering the CO₂-emission reductions needed. Upgrading the existing building stock is increasingly used as a method to address inefficiencies and a secure way to reduce emissions: by increasing the longevity of derelict unoccupied buildings through adaptive reuse, they become suitable sites for many different types of use.

This paper discusses the adaptive reuse of a former barrel factory in São Paulo to a popular leisure centre (Sesc) in Pompeia (1977 to 1986). Until today, the urban and sustainable dimension of Lina Bo Bardi's work in São Paulo has not been sufficiently discussed or appreciated. Until the Sesc Pompeia, the derelict factory was expected to be demolished to restart the development of the site with 'tabula rasa'. Besides Bo Bardi's social approach, there is also a strong environmental position that laid the foundation of sustainable urban renewal in Latin America. Bo Bardi's sustainable and socially-conscious design method is directly informed by her appreciation of the local and regional history of place. Her adaptive reuse of existing buildings therefore marks

a paradigm shift in thinking regarding existing historical structures in Brazil and the commencement of renovation as an eligible strategy for entire regenerated urban precincts. Lina Bo Bardi's robust concept was quite simple: "Retain as much of the existing building fabric as possible, working within the original envelope, providing new insertions to improve the circulation" (Ferraz 1993; Instituto LB and PM Bardi 2015).

Keywords: Adaptive reuse, up-cycling intervention, Lina Bo Bardi, modern heritage.

DEFINING THE LINK BETWEEN ADAPTIVE REUSE AND SUSTAINABILITY

Modernity and sustainability are closely intertwined in the challenge of creating better places to live and work. The existing built fabric represents a high value that offers a resource in terms of social, historical/cultural, economic and environmental sustainability. There is an opportunity and duty to preserve the existing fabric and reuse buildings which have lost their original function, are physically obsolete, or no longer meet today's ever-more demanding standards. It is part of a contemporary agenda of urban renewal to reuse the structure, material and space, to realise spatial and functional transformations and to update safety and efficiency concerning fire, user safety, energy efficiency and environmental comfort.

When linking adaptive reuse of old buildings with sustainability, there can be significant positive environmental and social impacts from conversions of existing buildings, beyond the sheer heritage value. The case study by architect Lina Bo Bardi (1914-1992) in São Paulo reduced the negative impact on the environment and the depletion of non-renewable resources. However, until today, the urban and environmental dimension of Bo Bardi's work has not been sufficiently discussed or appreciated. Besides her social approach, there is also a strong environmental position that laid the foundation of sustainable urban renewal in Latin America; and Bo Bardi's sustainable and socially-conscious design method is directly informed by the local and by regionalism. Keeping the existing buildings maintains the cultural identity and exemplifies the tectonic evolution of the vernacular architecture (Bergdoll 2015; Condello and Lehmann 2016b). In addition, it's a strategy that retains the embodied energy of the existing urban fabric and exemplifies the environmental significance of the existing structures.

In 1973-74, the challenge of the ecological crisis emerged, following the first Oil Crisis, and the publication of the pivotal book *The Limits to Growth* (Meadows, Randers, Behrens 1972). Both, the event and the text had many short-term and long-term effects on global politics and the economy, and generated a fervent debate (also between Brazil's intellectual circles). *The Limits to Growth* revealed that unlimited growth was impossible, given finite resource supplies and continuing population growth, marking a time when the *Ecological Architecture* movement emerged.

Sesc is the Serviço Social do Comércio, a union-led chain of leisure centres for Brazil's working class. Sesc leisure centres can be found in cities all over the country and some are also architecturally important.

Lina Bo Bardi's adaptive reuse of existing buildings for the Sesc in Pompeia marks a paradigm shift in thinking about historical structures in Brazil and the commencement of renovation as eligible strategy for entire urban precincts (and as alternative to the usual "tabula rasa" approach of Modernism). This was an entirely new paradigm, as the previous period of Modernism usually started with a *clean slate*, after the complete demolition of the existing old fabric to make space for the new (GIEDION 1941).

Following her early modernistic and structuralistic works, such as the Glass House (1949-51) or Masp Museum (1957-68) in São Paulo (both buildings still inspired by the International Style and Structuralism), the late thoughtful work of Bo Bardi is of an entirely different quality: recycling, up-cycling and adaptive reuse is applied as an urban design strategy where the *New* sits comfortably side-by-side with the *Old*, without ever imitating the existing (Lehmann 2004; Anelli 2015). Thus, Bo Bardi created her own continuation between dynamic vernacular and the modern avant-garde (Lehmann 2014, 142).

In regard to this resourcefulness and reuse, Zeuler Lima notes that "Bo Bardi's social and ethical awareness, and her talent for making do with scant resources – honed during her native Italy's World War II devastation – speaks to our anxious, solution-seeking era" (2013, 82). From the rejuvenation of a disused, neglected 1920s steel barrel factory into a public institution: the highly popular cultural and leisure centre Sesc Pompeia (1977-86), to the renewal of the historic Pelourinho district (the old Baroque centre of Salvador, 1986-92), such underutilized, abandoned or disused buildings and quarters are now seen as precious resources. Such sites and places can be transformed towards new usages and offer significant environmental and social benefits. Two cultural centres, Casa do Benin and Casa do Olodum (1987-89, both in Salvador) are further examples of the various specific restoration and reuse projects carried out as part of the rehabilitation of the historical centre, where new circulation systems and functional programmes were carefully inserted into existing structures (de Almeida Lima 2013; Oliveira 2014). These insertions of new structures respect rather than mimic its historic setting.

Adaptive reuse refers to the process of reusing an old existing building or site for a purpose other than which it was originally built or designed for. Design for reuse and durability includes the ability to satisfy changing user needs over time, emerging economic factors and complexity, and the *loose-fit* ability to integrate new technologies.

Reuse, recycling, recovering, repair and remanufacturing have all entered our vocabulary. To *reuse* (for example a building) is to use an item again after it has been used. This includes conventional reuse where the building is used again for the same function, and adaptive reuse, where it is used for a different function. In contrast, recycling is the breaking down of the used item into raw materials, which are then used to make new items. Thus, based on the embodied energy contained in the structure's material, the most sustainable building is the one that already exists (LEHMANN 2012).

Adaptive reuse, also known as *up-cycling* of buildings (or re-purposing), is the process of taking disused buildings that are now unwanted for their original function and transforming them again into a useful building (which is different from recycling, where the building materials are broken down to their component parts and re-manufactured into new parts, such as walls or floors). Adaptive reuse is also different from conventional reuse, where the product is used in its original purpose again.

Bo Bardi's approach to the disused factory was quite simple and robust: retaining as much of the existing building fabric as possible, working within the original envelope, providing new insertions such as staircases, to improve the circulation. Similar to today's Burra Charter, which recommends to do "as much as necessary, and as little as possible": all new work is made to read differently from the existing fabric so that the important qualities of the building's past have been identified and retained (such as the rich texture of the stonework and brick walls) (BARDI 1995/2012; OLIVEIRA 2006).

Through adaptive reuse of derelict, unoccupied buildings, these structures can become again suitable sites for many different types of use. Along with brownfield sites' reclamation, adaptive reuse is seen by many as a key factor in the reduction of urban sprawl and minimisation of construction waste (Condello and Lehmann 2016a). The increasing waste generation from construction and demolition is a growing worldwide concern. Instead of demolition, extending the lifecycle of buildings through their up-cycling and reuse is right at the core of any sustainability concept. By reusing an existing structure, the energy required to build these spaces is lessened, while the embodied energy in the building is maintained and the amount of new materials required for construction reduced; at the same time, the material waste that would come from destroying old buildings is also reduced (LEHMANN 2016).

Much of our cities' existing building stock predates modern energy standards and it is estimated that 80 per cent of buildings in existence

today will still be there in twenty years' time. It is therefore the physical improvements and upgrades to our existing buildings and neighbourhoods that will really deliver the CO₂-emission reductions needed. Upgrading the existing building stock is always a simple way to address inefficiencies and a secure way to reduce carbon emissions.

Industrial buildings and warehouses are frequently best suited to adaptive reuse, as they offer the maximum structural flexibility due to large span and high ceilings. Adaptive reuse can also be controversial if there is a blurred line between façadism (for example, only keeping a small token part of the existing building, such as its street façade wall), or can be a compromise with historic preservation to serve heritage policies. In addition, the cost of conversion can be prohibitive high, making it sometimes impossible to keep the existing structure (Whyte 1980; Abel 1997). Bo Bardi's projects have always avoided this trap and are strong evidence for the potential of true adaptive reuse at low cost and low environmental impact. It was always important for Bo Bardi to know exactly how the local community would benefit from the reuse of once abandoned sites or buildings. She recognised the importance of the factory space and instead of demolition, she proposed to maintain it – a novelty in Brazil at this time. The architect managed to convince and persuade the client that the idea to demolish the entire complex in order to restart with an empty site was not the best option, especially for a public centre that was supposed to be embraced by the local community.

Repurposing of old buildings can also be a valuable response to financial limitations. Today, local governments do sometimes provide financial incentives for adaptive reuse (for instance, generous support is available in Berlin), as there are many criteria that can affect the economic return of adaptive reuse (eg. there is always the risk of hidden costs in reusing older buildings and the danger of unknown contamination with asbestos or other toxic substances) when compared with new-built. Factors such as the reuse of materials and resources as well as a lesser need to involve energy, both in terms of labour and machine powered, can effectively decrease the funds needed for adaptive reuse. Determining the balance of how the several effects of adaptive reuse interact is often best accomplished by a formal lifecycle assessment (WARD 2012).

Implementing emission-reducing retrofits and gaining a better understanding of the actual performance benefits are early steps in the process to convince clients and municipalities. Retrofitting and modifying existing buildings and systems to greatly improve energy efficiency through relatively simple measures (eg. through insulation, high performance

glazing and so on) can represent the lowest cost route to reducing energy demand and carbon emissions. It is therefore beneficial to monitor and track the improved energy performance of up-cycled buildings, so that the financial basis for retrofit could be incentivised by rewarding measured success (Lehmann 2010). Today, the regeneration of former industrially used sites and the careful redevelopment of disused, derelict brownfield sites and buildings are a basic part of sustainable urban development.

Typical life-expectancy of different urban elements	
Commercial interiors	2-3 years
Building interior finishes	5-10 years
Building services	15-20 years
Building's usage	30 years
Building's structure	50+ years
Urban infrastructure (roads, railways)	100+ years
Cities and their urban blocks	500+ years

UP-CYCLING BUILDINGS AND RE-PURPOSING ABANDONED SITES: CASE STUDY SESC POMPEIA IN SÃO PAULO

The Sesc project exemplifies well the application of Bo Bardi's adaptive reuse principles and it is of particular relevance to her sensitive adaptive reuse work.

- Sesc Pompeia in São Paulo, 1977-78 and 1982-86 (Stage 1 was completed in 1978)

- The Sesc Fábrica da Pompeia cultural and leisure centre is one of Bo Bardi's most important projects and one of her largest one. Over a decade and several stages, the disused steel barrel and refrigerator factory was transformed into a public cultural and sports centre. Instead of demolition, the formerly industrial precinct was transformed step-by-step into a modern public facility for the Pompeia community. The existing ensemble of older industrial buildings had a specific authentic period character expressed through its brickworks, detailing of the roofs, steel windows and other features of the constructed eras that newer or reconstructed developments would have lacked. Bo Bardi carefully extended the reused ensemble with new buildings, such as a concrete tower of vertically stacked volleyball fields and swimming pool, heightening the awareness of the *new*. The cloud windows are evidence of her inventive playfulness.

Table 1 The typical life-expectancy of different elements in the built environment (after: McDonough and Braungart, 2003)

The determining criteria for the reuse of the old factory ensemble included:

- The societal value of the site and its importance to the community of workers that used to spend their lifetime on this site.
- The historical importance of the site, in this case especially the role of the former factory in the community's memory and understanding of the past.
- The potential for the reuse of the particular site. The physical damage was actually small and the site was ideal to support its future use as centre for culture, sports and leisure.

It is the project that most clearly exemplifies Bo Bardi's break with modernism: this adaptive re-use and extension of the former factory was environmentally sensitive and poetic at the same time, creating an assemblage and topography of old and new. There are various scales of intervention but the "new" is always respectful of the existing buildings and structures, designed with great precision and without any imitation. The Sesc Pompeia expresses Bo Bardi's core belief in an architecture that serves the masses without condescending to them. Inspired by San Francisco's renovated Ghirardelli Square (which was the first major adaptive re-use project in the United States, reusing a waterfront warehouse, which opened in 1964), the multi-use compound is like a village assembly of spaces and includes a swimming pool, a theatre, restaurants and exhibition galleries. The creation of such a diversity of interesting public spaces for the working people has significantly contributed to the health and cultural awareness of the residents in this working class neighbourhood, improving the level of access to public open spaces.

REAPPRAISING THE SESC POMPEIA

The Sesc Fábrica da Pompeia can be considered as a milestone in Bo Bardi's work: the conversion of the steel barrel and refrigerator factory into a very successful, much-loved leisure centre: it preserved the character, intrinsic substance and memory of the past through the reuse of the factory buildings. Initially, the original factory was due to be demolished and the new Sesc Pompeia would have replaced it. Bo Bardi, however, suggested that the factory be kept and not demolished as had been planned, but instead redeveloped, on the grounds that it was already informally colonised by some of the uses which the new centre was intended to serve. Firstly, many of the former workers still lived in the neighbourhood. Secondly, at her first site visit, Bo Bardi had realised that

the derelict factory was already informally occupied by people from the neighbourhood in a way it intended to be used for by SESC: there were active football teams, an lively amateur theatrical group, dance groups and improvised barbecue places. It was always important for Bo Bardi to first observe what was happening in the space naturally, before proceeding with her own design decisions. Always driven by an urge to design and build what people want, Bo Bardi noted: What we want is precisely to maintain and amplify what we've found here, nothing more (Ferraz 2012, at *Lina Bo Bardi: Together* exhibition web site, 2).

Bo Bardi proposed to strip back the existing building to its essence, exposing the beautiful but rough reinforced concrete structure and brick walls. The decision to keep the existing structure significantly enhanced the sense of place from a social point of view. There is a strong relationship between the existing factory and the local community, a working class district of São Paulo. The decision to keep the original factory paid respect to the history of human labour that took place there; in the words of Marcelo Ferraz, who worked as one of the architects on the Sesc Pompeia;

The rehabilitation of a former factory – a place of hard work; of suffering, for many; a testament to human labour – and its transformation into a place of leisure, without erasing its history, make Sesc Pompeia a special space. The care taken to ensure that so many details of the old factory remained visible – whether on walls, floors, roofs and other structures, or in the new facilities – meant the space would begin its new life full of warmth and animation. (Ferraz 2012, at *Lina Bo Bardi: Together* exhibition web site, 3)

Here, Bo Bardi's experiments with reinforced concrete, *beton brut*, continued, in combination with the reuse of the post-industrial brick shell of the abandoned factory. She later added three towers: a water tower and two 30m-high towers housing the sports courts and changing rooms. The whole project has a certain roughness and aims for a clear contrast between the new and the authentic old. Y-shaped bridges connect the towers, turning the journey from locker to court an event of circulation and urban drama. Being deeply committed to the social and cultural potential of architecture, Sesc Pompeia illustrates the power of architecture as *an agent of social change*, supporting residents of a poor working-class neighbourhood with cultural

and sports facilities, maintaining the identity, memory and history of place through careful adaptive reuse and extension.

Sesc Pompeia has a generosity in plan that allows its multiple activities to co-exist in a relaxed way: high and low culture, old and young, ambitious architecture and the everyday, football and ballet. Rowan Moore commented on the multi-functionality of the precinct:

It houses football, swimming, theatre, dance and art. Old men play chess there, and children play with building blocks. You can eat in a popular canteen, and you can sunbathe on a boardwalk called *The Beach*. Or you can simply sit and watch the passing scene, as you might in a park. (MOORE 2012)

Besides Bo Bardi, the main architects for the project were Andre Vainer and Marcelo Ferraz; the development of the project included input of many others. The project also included artists, technicians and workers in all aspects of the proposal, and Ferraz recounts the working process and participation of others:

André Vainer and I, first as students and then as recent graduates, were privileged to take part in this adventure. For nine years (1977–86) we developed the project with Lina, working every day in the midst of the building site: monitoring the ongoing projects, the in situ experiments, the involvement of technicians, artists, and especially workers...We had an office inside the building itself; the project and the programme were formulated as an amalgam, joined and inseparable. The barrier that would normally separate the virtual and the real did not exist; it was architecture made real, experienced in every detail. (Ferraz 2012, at *Lina Bo Bardi: Together* exhibition web site, 4)

Considering the importance of collaboration in the design and construction process, Bo Bardi's goal was to place people at the forefront of all design decisions, not just the direct end-users, but the wider community. According to her former collaborators (Vainer and Ferraz), she had very clear ideas how she wanted the spaces to function, making sure that everything was aimed to create a sense of leisure within the project. The purpose of design is to facilitate the building's ability to invite the user to

participate in certain social situations and activities, and Sesc Pompeia is doing this very well. Bo Bardi's careful and considerate adaptive reuse work has recently become popular among the younger generation of architects, many of whom have been embracing enthusiastically her oeuvre, mainly thanks to a growing interest in projects with a social and cultural conscience.

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